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THE ROLE OF THE STUDENT UNION IN DEMOCRATIC MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The research showed the potential of analyzing the role of the student union in engaging students in a culture of participation in pedagogical activities that can really contribute to democratic management and the learning process in everyday school life. The general aim of this research was to analyze the role of the student council in democratic management and its contributions to the learning process. The research used a qualitative approach and the extended case method with semi-structured interviews to capture data.